

D6.2 Exploitation, communication and dissemination plan for ArcSolution

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Executive summary

The ArcSolution team is investigating Arctic pollution in a One Health perspective. The project focusses on four study locations: Northern Norway, Northern Finland (Inari), Greenland, Svalbard (Longyearbyen). Since the project is built on a participatory approach, much of the communication with local experts, stakeholders, students and the public will proceed in continuous dialogues rather than one-way communication.

Many local contacts were already established in the planning phase of ArcSolution, to ensure co-creation from early stages on. In addition, ArcSolution results will be communicated to a variety of target audiences, including policymakers at local, regional, national and international level, industry, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), community stakeholders and the research community (Tabel 1). This communication will proceed via multiple parallel channels and use several tools, such as the project webpage (including a news section), digital newsletters, policy briefs, popular science reports and scientific publications. In addition, educational programs and tools have a central role in the ArcSolution research and communication program and aim to involve pupils and students at different educational levels in Citizen Science and outreach activities. The project will be integrated in existing curricula if the school expresses this interest.

Exploitation is highlighted in the solution-oriented approach of ArcSolution, involving local companies, policymakers, students and interest organisations that will exploit the results of ArcSolution in different ways. The communication plan is a living document, and at the end of the project, a dedicated Deliverable will summarize and report on the exploitation, communication and dissemination activities in ArcSolution.

Table1: Summary of communication activities and priorities in ArcSolution

Target audience	Main responsibility	Project activity	Channels	Comments
Academia and research communities	Initiated by individual researchers in agreement with WP leaders	Publications, presentations	Scientific papers in open-access journals, conferences, workshops	In accordance with the publication strategy in ArcSolution
Policy makers at national and international level, e.g. UNEP	WP 6	Information of project results; policy briefs	Meetings, publications	Planned for the final phase of the project
EU	WP 6	Involvement in EU Polar Cluster and other activities; policy briefs; newsletters	Meetings; Research & innovation success stories Horizon Magazine Cordis Results in Brief CORDIS covery podcasts Website, project officer	Coordination and collaboration with ILLUQ and ICEBERG
Local experts and authorities at local level	WP5, WP 6, WP 2 and partners at the study locations	Dialogue on local interests and project results;	Newsletters, popular science communication,	Can be combined with annual

		knowledge transfer to local experts	policy briefs, seminars, townhall meetings	workshops at the study locations
Local community at the study locations	WP5, WP 6, WP 2 and partners at the study locations	Dialogue on local interests and project results	Local newspapers, videos townhall meetings social media	Use of local communication platforms and local languages
Schools	WP 6, WP 2 and partners at the study locations	Teaching; Citizen Science projects; student involvement in outreach	Teams platform for exchange among schools, all other channels possible, depending on the students' interests	Formalized collaboration with schools at all study locations, established since the planning phase
Project participants	WP1	Information in the project group; discussion of scientific and practical topics	Teams, internal newsletter, meeting, project website and Some	Internal communication described in Project Handbook

0 Preface

ArcSolution – Arctic Pollution in a One Health Perspective: From complex challenges to sustainable solutions is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (Grant No. 101135051). The project runs from August 2024 to July 2028. ArcSolution is coordinated by Nord University (Bodø, Norway) and has eleven partners from five countries, plus three associated partners from Switzerland, Canada and China. The project is funded through the call “Tackling human and climate change induced pollution in the Arctic – building resilient socio-ecological systems” (Zero Pollution-01-3). Under the same call, two other activities are supported: ILLUQ (coordinated by Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Germany) and ICEBERG (coordinated by the University of Oulu, Finland). All three projects form a thematic Arctic project cluster under the “Zero-Pollution” collaboration.

The Grant Agreement for ArcSolution specifies in Article 17 that “*the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) [...] in a strategic, coherent and effective manner*”. In all communication and dissemination activities, the funding source must be acknowledged in accordance with Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement.

1 Introduction

The Arctic is undergoing rapid changes due to climate change and socio-economic developments in the region. Pollution is a major stressor in the Arctic, resulting from long-range transport of mid-latitude emissions as well as local sources including inadequate waste management. ArcSolution approaches Arctic pollution and associated risks in a One Health approach, recognizing the interlinkages of human, environmental and animal health. The Arc Solution One Health approach will assess the pollution situation in the context of climate change at four different study locations in the European Arctic: Northern Norway, Northern Finland (Inari), Greenland and Svalbard (Longyearbyen) As an integrated ArcSolution strategy the project will study the impact on ecosystems and humans while developing solutions for local adaptation. In addition, the associated partner from Canada will add corresponding information from some Canadian locations, for example the Mackenzie region in Canada.

ArcSolution uses a transdisciplinary approach that integrates environmental, health, social and technical sciences with local and Indigenous knowledge. Besides the pre-defined pollutants per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), mercury (Hg), plastics (and plastic additives), the project works with locally defined priorities. The research strategy is based on participatory approaches, which already started during the planning and writing phase of the ArcSolution proposal including education and citizen science projects. The outcomes are expected to inform policy recommendations, enhance resilience and foster sustainable developments in the Arctic.

The project is organized in six work packages (WPs), each comprising five tasks. The study locations cut across these WPs (Figure 1). WP6 is dedicated to link the WP outcomes as well as exploitation, communication and dissemination of the project results. All partners are involved in WP6 and will contribute actively to exploitation, communication and dissemination actions.

2 The participatory approach

The participatory approach is the basis for ArcSolution research. The researchers in ArcSolution collaborate on equal terms with local municipalities, schools and experts in all steps of the project, from the original planning to communication and dissemination of results. This collaboration proceeds in a co-creation process on the topics addressed in the WPs of ArcSolution (Figure 1), creating community-based participatory research (CBPR). CBPR is conducted in a respectful partnership with shared decision-making and equitable power distribution between community stakeholders, local experts and the academic partner institutions. At least one Citizen Science project is planned at each study location.

Figure 1: Structure of ArcSolution including six work packages and addressing four study locations

The participatory approach in ArcSolution creates a communication situation where members of a typical target audience (e.g. local stakeholders, municipalities, schools, Indigenous peoples) are involved in defining, planning and implementing activities in ArcSolution. Hence, much of the communication in ArcSolution is not expected to proceed in one direction, but rather in dialogue addressing all phases of the project. This also implies that local partners may have suggestions for communication actions, channels and tools that will be considered along with those in section 5. As part of the participatory approach, local workshops arranged at each of the study locations will ensure the close dialogue and continuous feedback from local stakeholders and the public. Starting workshops have been held at each study location within the first six months of ArcSolution and follow-up workshops will be arranged annually.

ArcSolution has a special focus on educating and informing the young generation, as participants in Citizen Science Projects, co-creators of communication and dissemination materials as well as a target group for information on Arctic pollution. For this reason, educational aspects will be a central element of ArcSolution including its communication and dissemination activities, as detailed in Section 5.7.

Local communication at the four study locations will mainly use local platforms such as news media and social channels that are already established and in use to inform the public and

relevant stakeholders. Specifically, it has already been agreed with the communication platform arctichub.gl in Greenland that they will inform about ArcSolution. Translations into Greenlandic have been offered by the project partner Ilisimatusarfik. Since ICEBERG and ILLUQ also operate in Longyearbyen, it has also been agreed to coordinate the local communication among the three projects, including joint communication products.

3 Dissemination and communication objectives

In addition to participatory communication during the project, the results of the projects are targeted at a variety of audiences and stakeholders, as described below. Dissemination and communication objectives differ according to the target audiences. Hence, the ArcSolution communication strategies and tools will be optimized for different recipient groups. As illustration, a non-exhaustive list of objectives of dissemination and communication activities in ArcSolution is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Examples of dissemination and communication objectives in ArcSolution

Raise awareness of Arctic pollution and its effect on ecosystems and humans in the public and with decision makers
Involve students in ArcSolution, as researchers, audience and communicators
Create an understanding of interlinkages and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in a One Health perspective
Convey the complexity of Arctic pollution, from sources to effects
Involve stakeholders and the public in exchange of information on Arctic pollution
Increase motivation to search for solutions and ensure ownership for actions at local level
Support policy and regulation actions to protect the Arctic environment and its inhabitants
Share new findings from ArcSolution to expand the scientific knowledge base
Connect ArcSolution with other related research and communication activities in the field
Propose solutions, strategies and integrated actions at local, regional, national and international level to reduce Arctic pollution
Provide ideas and recommendations for realistic and locally anchored solutions to pollution problems in the Arctic
Collaboration with joint ZERO POLLUTION cluster projects, ILLUQ and ICEBERG
Share results of the project in scientific platform, e.g., in publications, conferences, workshops

4 Target audiences

The participatory approach of ArcSolution relies on the active involvement of the local communities in the integrated design, operation and communication of the project activities. Students, in particular, are expected to contribute actively to the project. As they might also define target audiences for their activities, the list in Table 3 includes target groups foreseen at this stage of the project but will be flexible for potential adjustments.

Table 3: Expected target audiences in ArcSolution

Academia and research communities
The general public at the study locations, including local and Indigenous communities, also in the wider Arctic area

Local experts and professionals in the study fields of ArcSolution, for example fishermen, hunters, reindeer herders, aquaculture experts
Schools and other educational institutions at the study locations (pupils and teachers)
Health authorities and relevant experts at the local, national and international level (e.g. WHO)
Policy makers and regulators in the field of chemicals management at local, national, European and international level
Industry and professional interest organisations
Non-governmental organizations focussing on environmental issues
Municipalities and community experts
Technology developers and related industries, e.g. in environmental engineering

5 Dissemination and communication action and tools

Considering the connections foreseen in the exploitation of the project results (section 8), ArcSolution will use communication and dissemination tools and actions that efficiently reach all important target groups including the public, schools, policymakers and academia. Students and teachers are important participants and target groups of ArcSolution at the same time, as specified in section 6. An overview of different dissemination and communication tools and the targeted audiences is provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of communication tools and target audiences

	Public	Local experts	Educational institutions	Health authorities	Policy makers	Industry	Scientific community
Social media							
Newsletter							
Popular science communication							
Policy briefs							
Teaching material							
Scientific publications							

5.1 Graphical identity of ArcSolution

The project team has created a logo that shows the wide Arctic focus of the project (Figure 2). The graphic presentation illustrates the comprehensive geographical relevance of the ArcSolution initiative. This ArcSolution emblem shows the project name where “Solution” is spelled out, symbolising the importance of sustainable Solutions as the overarching aim of the project. The logo is available to all project partners and is already used actively for all ArcSolution presentations and messages. Templates have been prepared for presentations about ArcSolution, ensuring coordinated approaches and graphical recognizability. The ArcSolution logo will be presented in combination with the EU commission logo in all official project documents and presentations.

Figure 2: Logo for ArcSolution

5.2 Communication languages

The general language for communication in ArcSolution is English. However, the project respects and supports the use of different languages in the project group and at the study locations, provided it does not create situations of exclusion. Dissemination and communication actions with local and indigenous communities as target audiences will include material in their own language, i.e. Danish, Finnish, Greenlandic, Norwegian, and Sámi languages.

5.3 Online tools

The ArcSolution webpage is <https://arcsolution.eu>

The webpage includes a presentation of the project and the partners as well as a News section, which will be updated regularly. The webpage will be maintained by the coordinating institution at least three years beyond the duration of the project, to inform about ArcSolution results.

ArcSolution has already established accounts on LinkedIn and Facebook which will be continuously updated with news and relevant information on events, activities and publications. Online communication in ArcSolution will be linked with the corresponding channels of the partner institution and vice versa.

All young scientists (PhD fellows & Postdocs) working with ArcSolution will be encouraged to develop their own blogs and related communication platforms for direct communication with fellow scientists and the interested public.

5.4 Newsletters

Newsletters are prepared in ArcSolution for different purposes, i.e. for internal communication (see section 7) and for external information about the project. External audiences include the scientific community, the sister projects ILLUQ and ICEBERG, policy makers, schools, industry and intergovernmental organisations with a focus on the Arctic (e.g. Arctic Council).

Newsletters are typically short (about 2-4 pages) and include summaries of recent highlights of the project and updates on progress. Newsletters for internal use, i.e. for the information of the consortium, are prepared every few weeks or months, depending on activities and news in the project.

5.5 Popular science communication

The homepage includes a News section with information about activities and findings in the project that project members would like to share. This news may also be published in the other ArcSolution media channels in a condensed way.

Popular science communication is encouraged in ArcSolution and can have different formats such as articles in national languages in newspapers and scientific magazines, presentations at local or regional events, townhall meetings etc. Popular science communication also includes press releases, typically about a specific topic, in different languages, preferably involving local connections and communication platforms, e.g., arctichub.gl and Sámi News. It may also include interactions with non-governmental organisations (NGOs) on the topic of Arctic pollution and health and presentations at public events relevant for the target audiences (e.g. fairs, public meetings).

Popular science communication includes written products, videos, podcasts, oral presentations and discussions and art performances. Several countries and towns arrange popular science events where ArcSolution can be presented. Examples include Greenland Science Week (<https://www.scienceweek.gl>), Arctic Frontiers in Tromsø (<https://arcticfrontiers.com/>), Science Day in Denmark etc.

The ArcSolution WP leader team arrange regular weekly meeting every Tuesday to discuss the progress of the project. These meetings include mutual information about recent and upcoming publications. The WP leaders will discuss in this forum whether the results of the publications should be communicated via other channels and to other audiences. For example, a scientific publication could be summarized in a popular science article or a podcast requiring a different style, potentially translated to different languages. It might be relevant to inform about project products on social media, local workshops, in newsletters etc. Based on the discussion in the WP leader group, a spin-off activity will be proposed to the corresponding author of the publication. WP6 leader will take responsibility for following up. He will also be responsible for notifying relevant stakeholders, including consortium partners and key contacts, to broaden the reach.

5.6 Policy briefs

Based on the scientific results of ArcSolution, high-level summaries and proposals for policymakers will be prepared for decision-making and -implementation at different geographical scales.

ArcSolution's workplan includes two deliverables in the format of policy briefs:

- D2.7: Policy brief 1
This policy brief is under the responsibility of the University of Oulu, due in Month 15 and connected with T2.4.
It will be prepared in collaboration with ICEBERG and ILLUQ about the local priorities identified at the common study locations, i.e. Svalbard and Greenland
- D6.7: Policy brief 2
This policy brief is under the responsibility of Arctic Knowledge, due in Month 46 and connected with T6.3
It will include recommendations for actions based on science, considering all outcomes of ArcSolution in an integrated way.

The policy briefs are intended to include illustrations and other arts and graphics from the Citizen Science Projects and collaboration with the schools, if the timelines match with the Citizen Science Projects. Policy briefs can be delivered in different ways. They can be presented at meetings with the target group (policy makers), in person or online, and/or published in the open literature. Relevant political representatives can be specifically invited to these meetings.

5.7 Educational and training material

As specified in section 6, education is a central activity in ArcSolution, which includes different types of communication. Specifically, ArcSolution will produce toolboxes with materials and activities about One Health topics, environment, pollution issues and solutions, targeting different age groups of pupils and students. The Citizen Science Projects which are included in the schools will use networks for dissemination of the results of their products, which can be their own or suggested by ArcSolution. WP6 will coordinate and disseminate these activities to a broader audience.

ArcSolution will also engage in Summer Schools and/or courses for international postgraduate and PhD students, teachers and interested stakeholders in the Arctic countries. These schools and courses can be organized in collaboration with the University of the Arctic, the Norwegian Polar Research Academy, the NUNAMED conference in Greenland, and possibly other interested organisations. They can include combinations of lectures, field work, laboratory work and seminars, with guidance from the ArcSolution researchers.

Educational courses will be developed at the Institute of Sámi Education in Finland, and additional activities will be established at schools at the other locations. These are described in Chapter 6.

5.8 ArcSolution deliverables

ArcSolution includes 37 contractual deliverables that will report specific results of the project, most of them as public reports. They will be published on the ArcSolution webpage after their approval by the Project Officer. Prior to submission, the draft deliverables will be quality assured according to a procedure described in the ArcSolution project handbook.

5.9 Scientific publications and presentations

The scientific results of ArcSolution will be published in the peer-reviewed scientific literature according to the Open Science strategy which includes open access (gold standard: <https://open-access.network/en/information/open-access-primers/green-and-gold>). Publications that are based on ArcSolution and contain ArcSolution results must refer to the funding source in the Acknowledgements, in accordance with Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement.

The Open Science strategy relies on open cooperative work, including open access to publications and to research data. All scientific publications in ArcSolution must be open access, as specified in the Grant Agreement. Journal articles will be published under a CC BY license, while books will be published open access under a Creative Commons (or stricter) license. Authors will state their ORCID and ensure that sufficient Intellectual Property Rights are retained. All scientific publications will also be deposited in NORD's institutional repository and published on the project webpage.

The results of ArcSolution will also be presented at relevant scientific conferences. The ArcSolution consortium will arrange an open international conference towards the end of the project, where results of the project will be presented together with external presentations by experts in the field.

The scientific publications, including conference presentations, follow the following publication strategy that aims to ensure a transparent and inclusive process: All scientific publications of

ArcSolution results are encouraged and can be initiated by any partner in the project. As a first step, the relevant WP leader is informed about the intended publication. In addition, the planned publication is entered into the excel spreadsheet that has been prepared for this purpose and that is accessible to all project partners via Teams. Progress with the preparation of the scientific publication is indicated in the excel spreadsheet (status column: in preparation, submitted etc.).

6 Education

Education is a central activity in ArcSolution, recognizing the young generation's interest in environmental questions and the importance of comprehensive information based on current scientific knowledge. ArcSolution has the ambition of informing about the complexity of Arctic pollution and climate change, and their interactions, and the active involvement of students and teachers in different parts of the project is important.

We intend to incorporate ArcSolution in existing courses and programmes on natural resources, pollution and food safety and security, in collaboration with education institutes at the study locations. ArcSolution already established contacts with schools at the study locations in the planning phase of the project. Regular and open communication between ArcSolution and the schools has already taken place and is expected to continue throughout the project. Ideas from the schools are welcome throughout the project, subject to feasibility. Further, education of professionals will also be included in the ArcSolution educational programme. This may include specialisation courses on specific topics developed together with educational institutions or other interested organisations, such as municipalities and local expert organisations at the study locations.

ArcSolution has established cooperations (since the phase of the application writing) with the following schools at all study locations:

- Institute for Sámi Education in Inari (Finland)
- Folkehøgskolen i Longyearbyen (Svalbard)
- Videregående Skole (High school) i Longyearbyen (Svalbard)
- Videregående Skole Kongsbakken (High school) in Tromsø (Norway)
- Videregående Skole (High school) with a focus on fisheries and aquaculture on Skjervøy (Norway)
- Greenland Business School (Greenland)

Education is incorporated in ArcSolution in several ways:

6.1 Information to students

Teaching materials will be prepared on Arctic pollution in the One Health context for different age groups. If there is an interest from the school, ArcSolution researchers can give lectures on topics of their disciplines.

6.2 Citizen Science projects

Based on their interests and in line with capacity in their respective curricula, pupils and students can define their own projects where ArcSolution scientists have a consulting role. Examples that have been suggested by the schools and discussed in meetings during site visits include (but will not be limited to)

- Visualisation and graphical communication of local pollution in Svalbard
- Measurements and assessment of local pollution in fjords in Svalbard
- Local marine fish as carrier of pollutants in Tromsø
- Indoor measurements in schools in Svalbard to monitor air quality
- Sustainable technologies in modern aquaculture
- Science project focusing on health of environment, wildlife and pollution

Citizen Science projects are planned to be tied to the existing curriculum of the school. Once the project ends, these projects may continue as part of the school curriculum in following years as well.

6.3 Involvement of students in outreach activities

The communication and dissemination of the results is an integrated part of the Citizen Science projects that pupils and students will conduct. In addition, they can design communication and dissemination activities for their peers. They are also invited to contribute to policy briefs (see section 5.6) and other outreach activities.

6.4 Teachers

The local teachers will be involved in all activities planned at the schools in the framework of ArcSolution. The teacher will advise the research team on priorities in relation to the current curriculum and will serve as contact person for the pupils and the ArcSolution researchers during the project work. They will be informed about the topics of ArcSolution and will support the development and use of the material that ArcSolution produces as teaching support.

7 Internal communication

The internal communication in ArcSolution follows the activities detailed in T1.3. It includes annual in person consortium meetings and online meetings in the consortium and specific groups (e.g. tasks or topic groups) as needed.

Internal communication tools and procedures are further detailed in the project handbook, including the following items:

- Microsoft Teams as the main platform for information exchange and documentation, supported by additional email circulation of important information and documents.
- Email distribution lists should be kept updated for each partner
- It is the responsibility of the contact person in each partner organisation to inform within his/her organisation

As mentioned in section 5.4, internal newsletters are prepared regularly to inform the consortium, about activities and the progress of the project.

The ArcSolution early carrier scientist group (i.e. PhD fellows and postdocs) will develop and organise their own seminar series with digital presentations by young researchers. In-person meetings can be arranged at one of the host universities as appropriate.

8 Exploitation plan

Outcomes of ArcSolution will be scientific documentation for technological, environmental and societal improvements. Relevant ArcSolution results will serve as foundation for policies and regulations in the field of chemicals management and protection of environment and health. Our comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy will ensure that the results of the project will be available for uptake and implementation by relevant target groups. Anchoring the activities with local stakeholders will create local ownership for the implementation of sustainable solutions.

Increasing the awareness of citizens to avoid pollution is an obvious first step in the exploitation of the project results, since this awareness will support behavioural adjustments, e.g. dietary choices, reduced use of plastics and purchase of eco-labelled products. Changes in consumer behaviour might influence regulatory authorities as well as businesses. This can lead to a second step in the exploitation, changes implemented by policymakers and industry.

The transdisciplinary research in ArcSolution will include the development of new analytical approaches and technological solutions. These will create a platform for pollution mitigation strategies. For example, a circular bioeconomic strategy in the Arctic will contribute to a more efficient utilization of resources and sustainable production processes in fisheries, aquaculture and other relevant industries. It will be an important component in waste and wastewater treatment in the Arctic, since a stronger focus on recycling and upcycling has the potential to generate resources for new products such as biogas and fertilisers. ArcSolution contributes to the development and implementation of these promising technologies in the Arctic, based on locally anchored approaches, and ensures their sustainability and quality from a One Health perspective.

Exploitation of the results will be addressed in the participatory approaches, including the Citizen Science projects and school projects, to ensure impacts and sustainability at the local level. Table 5 lists examples of target groups who can exploit the results of ArcSolution and associated project outputs. Several partners have Technology Transfer units or similar offices at their institutions who will support the exploitation initiatives in ArcSolution.

Table 5: Expected exploitation results and target groups

Target group	ArcSolution outputs	Exploitation tools	Indicators
Local and Indigenous communities	Information about exposure risks	Dialogue on how to reduce exposure risks	Reduced internal exposure levels
Schools / students	Observations from their own projects; communication of ArcSolution	Teaching materials; citizen science projects; outreach activities	Inclusion in curricula
Local authorities	Co-created solutions	Local applications	Operation
Policy makers (regional, national, international scales)	Science-based advice	Policy briefs; presentations	Uptake by regulatory system
Industry	New findings about pollution and risks	Development of safe products	Reduced emissions
Scientific community	New scientific results	Scientific publications by the ArcSolution consortium	Number of publications and citations

Local companies	Technologies for local applications	Collaboration on tests and implementation	Implemented solutions
Other research initiatives	New scientific results of common interest	Exchange	New combined initiatives or use of data and infrastructure
Technological development and spin-off	New technological solutions to be commercialised	Lab-testing and up-scaling	Economic prospects and sustainable solutions

9 Concluding exploitation, communication and dissemination report (D6.6)

At the end of the project, the exploitation, communication and dissemination activities in ArcSolution will be summarized in D6.6.